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**THE HUMOR OF INEXPLICABLE THINGS: A QUALITATIVE
COMPARISON BETWEEN MEME MARKETING AND VIRAL
MARKETING**

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ABSTRACT

Meme marketing and viral marketing share some similarities despite being different marketing strategies. Both are built upon spraedable, interesting, and entertaining content, While viral marketing has been a popular marketing strategy for many years, meme marketing has emerged as a new and potentially more effective approach in the digital age. Although both strategies rely on shareable, entertaining content, meme marketing is more targeted and personalized than viral marketing, which tends to have a broader reach. Additionally, meme marketing aims to increase engagement and interaction with the audience, while viral marketing is often more passive in its approach. Thus, it can be argued that meme marketing offers a more tailored and engaging way to connect with consumers and promote brand messaging. The study will use the methodology of a case study to compare the effectiveness of meme marketing and viral marketing as marketing strategies. A case study is an appropriate methodology for this research because it allows for an in-depth analysis of specific cases, which can provide insights into the benefits and drawbacks of each marketing strategy in different contexts. The case study will involve analyzing the marketing campaigns of two companies, one using viral marketing and the other using meme marketing, to compare their respective outcomes in terms of brand awareness, engagement, and sales. By using a case study approach, this research aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of the differences between meme marketing and viral marketing, and their relative effectiveness as marketing strategies.

Keywords: Humor in Marketing Campaigns, Popular Culture, Internet Meme, Meme Marketing, Viral Marketing.

**İZAHİ OLMAYAN ŞEYLERİN MİZAHİ : MİM PAZARLAMA VE
VİRAL PAZARLAMA ARASINDA NİTEL BİR KARŞILAŞTIRMA**

ÖZET

Meme pazarlama ve viral pazarlama, farklı pazarlama stratejileri olsa da, bulaştırılabilir, ilginç ve eğlenceli içerikler üzerine kuruludur. Viral pazarlama uzun yıllardır popüler bir pazarlama stratejisi olmasına rağmen, meme pazarlama dijital çağda yeni ve potansiyel olarak daha etkili bir yaklaşım olarak ortaya çıkmıştır. Her iki strateji de paylaşılabılır, eğlenceli içeriklere dayandığından, meme pazarlama, daha kapsamlı bir kitleye sahip olan viral pazarlamadan daha hedefe yönelik ve kişiselleştirilmiştir. Ayrıca, meme pazarlama hedef kitle ile etkileşimi artırmayı amaçlarken, viral pazarlama genellikle daha pasiftir. Böylece, tüketicilerle bağlantı kurmak ve marka mesajlarını tanıtmak için daha özel ve etkileyici bir yol sunduğu düşünülebilir. Bu çalışma, pazarlama stratejileri olarak meme pazarlaması ve viral pazarlamanın etkililiğini karşılaştırmak için durum çalışması metodolojisini kullanacaktır. Bir durum çalışması, her bir pazarlama stratejisinin farklı bağlamlarda avantaj ve dezavantajlarına dair anlayış sağlayabilecek özel vakaların derinlemesine analizine izin veren uygun bir metodolojidir. Bu durum çalışması, biri viral pazarlama diğeri ise meme pazarlama kullanan iki şirketin pazarlama kampanyalarının analizini içerecek ve marka bilinirliği, etkileşim ve satış gibi konulardaki sonuçlarını karşılaştıracaktır. Bir durum çalışması yaklaşımı kullanarak, bu araştırma meme pazarlaması ve viral pazarlama arasındaki farklılıkların ve pazarlama stratejilerinin göreceli etkililiğinin daha ayrıntılı bir anlayışını sunmayı amaçlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Pazarlama Çalışmalarında Mizah, İnternet Mimi, Popüler Kültür, Mim Pazarlama, Viral Pazarlama

Objectives of the Research

Examine the similarities and differences between meme marketing and viral marketing. Investigate the potential advantages and disadvantages of meme marketing compared to viral marketing. Provide insights into the benefits and drawbacks of meme marketing and viral marketing in different contexts through an in-depth case study analysis. Offer a more nuanced understanding of the differences between meme marketing and viral marketing as well as their relative effectiveness as marketing strategies.

Definitions of Meme Content and Viral Content

Memes; could be an image, video, piece of text, etc., typically humorous in nature, that is copied and spread rapidly by internet users, often with slight variations.[1][2]

Virals; are online content that achieves a high level of awareness due to shares and exposure on social media networks, news websites, aggregators, email newsletters and search engines.[6]

Figure 1 and 2 : Viral Content vs. Meme Content (Gangnam Style, Hide the Pain Harold)

Difference Between Viral Marketing and Meme Marketing

While viral content spread through sharing, meme content spread through imaginatively repurposing the original material. Existing research has studied the causes of these activities, and they are distinguishable [3]. Viral content is online content that achieves a high level of awareness due to shares and exposure on social media networks, news websites, aggregators, email newsletters and search engines [4].

Virals Are Temporary

Viral content in marketing is only usable for the short period of time when they become popular. They do not have any intention to convey a message or make people think, and there is no hidden message [5]. Viral content tends to have a temporary nature because its popularity and widespread sharing are often short-lived. It can quickly gain attention and generate a high level of engagement, but its impact may diminish as new trends and topics emerge.

Figure 3 and 4: Meme Contents Spreads with Slightly Different Variations. (Distracted Boyfriend)

Unlike viral content, memes propagate by being shared with slight modifications. These alterations can involve changing the written captions, adding or removing characters, or even completely transforming the scene. Consequently, memes have the ability to endure over time and reach larger audiences, transcending geographical boundaries. The "Distracted Boyfriend" meme, depicted in Figure 3, originated from a street photograph taken by Antonio Guillem and uploaded to a stock photo website in 2015. Over the years, people began sending the image to one another with different messages, as shown in Figure 5. This particular meme, which remains widely recognized today, serves as an example of how memes can be more impactful than viral content in marketing.

Figure 5: Variations of the Same Meme in Years. (Distracted Boyfriend)

Memes Remains Relevant Thanks to Their Versatility

In contrast, meme content possesses characteristics that contribute to its enduring presence and longevity. These characteristics include versatility and relatability, which enable memes to remain relevant, shared, and referenced even after the initial surge of virality subsides. Memes have the ability to adapt and evolve through small modifications, such as altering captions, adding or removing elements, or completely transforming the context [5]. This adaptability allows memes to resonate with a wide range of individuals and communities, transcending cultural, linguistic, and geographical boundaries. As a result, memes can maintain their appeal and continue to be circulated and engaged with by diverse audiences over an extended period. This sustained presence and ongoing dissemination of meme content exemplify its potential to endure and thrive beyond the temporary nature of viral content.

Dollar Shave Club Case

Dollar Shave Club, a mail-order subscription service for personal care products, was established in 2011 by Michael Dubin and Mark Levine [7]. Michael Dubin, a former digital

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marketing executive, conceived the idea in response to the high prices of razor blades. In March 2012, the company made its official debut with a clever viral video that rapidly gained attention and helped establish its brand. Dollar Shave Club experienced swift success, thanks to its affordable pricing and innovative subscription model, offering customers a range of convenient and cost-effective options for razors and shaving products. On July 19, 2016, multinational consumer goods company Unilever acquired Dollar Shave Club for a reported \$1 billion in cash, recognizing the substantial value and potential of the subscription-based business model. The current worth of Dollar Shave Club is not publicly available [8].

Dollar Shave Club's Video Gone Viral

The success of Dollar Shave Club can be attributed to their direct response marketing approach, which focused on rapidly building a paying user base. They achieved this through a highly successful short-form sales video that generated significant traffic and new subscribers. The video began by presenting their offer upfront, addressing potential objections, and highlighting the quality of their razors [9].

[DollarShaveClub.com - Our Blades Are F***ing Great](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1p831111111)

YouTube · Dollar Shave Club · 6 Mar 2012

Figure 6: “Our Blades are F***ing Great” Commercial

The use of humor throughout the video helped engage the audience. The speaker emphasizes the importance of effective calls to action and the use of logical reasoning to support the product's value. Overall, the video exemplifies successful short-form direct-response marketing with its combination of humor, strategic messaging, and clear calls to action.

Figure 6: DailyWire's “Jeremy's Razors” Commercial

The effects of DSC (Dollar Shave Club) emerged when Harry's entered the market. Later, due to political reasons, they removed their advertisement from DailyWire. In response, DW created a striking advertisement, similar to the initial launch of other's monthly razor subscription, and released a grooming set under the brand "Jeremys" as a promotional stunt [10]. This demonstrates the effectiveness of viral marketing in the past decade. However, meme marketing will dominate in the next 10 years.

Scrub Daddy Case

Scrub Daddy is a company that produces and sells innovative cleaning products, most notably its signature sponge. It was founded by Aaron Krause in 2006. The company gained significant attention after appearing on the television show "Shark Tank" in 2012, where it secured a deal (200.000 US Dollars for %20 of the company) with investor Lori Greiner.

Scrub Daddy's unique sponge, which changes texture based on water temperature, became a hit with consumers. Scrub Daddy's exact net worth is not publicly disclosed. However, it has experienced substantial growth and success, expanding its product line and gaining a strong presence in the cleaning market [11].

Figure 7: Scrub Daddy Logo

Early Success of Scrub Daddy

The Scrub Daddy sponge quickly gained popularity due to its distinctive design and versatile functionality. It features a patented FlexTexture® material that adjusts its texture based on water temperature, allowing it to provide different scrubbing options for various cleaning tasks. The sponge's smiley face shape adds a touch of fun to the cleaning experience.

After the Shark Tank [12], Scrub Daddy has appeared multiple times on the QVC tele-shopping program, where they have introduced several new products. Some of these products include Scrub Mommy and Scrub Daisy, among others.

Figure 8: CEO Aaron Krause giving a business pitch in Shark Tank TV Show in 2012

Scrub Daddy's Meme Marketing Posts

Scrub Daddy employs meme marketing strategies by incorporating popular internet memes into their promotional content. One example of this is evident in their video titled "Giga Daddy," where they utilize the Giga Chad meme. By leveraging the existing popularity and recognition of the Giga Chad meme within online communities, Scrub Daddy taps into the meme's appeal and relevance to capture the attention of their target audience.

Figure 9: Giga Daddy Video gets 6.5 Million on Youtube and 28 Million on Tiktok in 4 months

The Giga Chad meme originated in 2017 and is linked to a nickname given to the subjects depicted in a series of edited photographs by Russian photographer Krista Sudmalis for her project Sleek'N'Tears. The term "Giga Chad" represents an exaggerated portrayal of Chad Thundercock, an internet archetype that symbolizes an extremely masculine and sexually attractive male figure. The meme has become popular in a range of online communities, including those associated with incels [13]

Figure 10: The Giga Chad Meme

One instance of the Giga Chad meme being utilized is in a video produced by Scrub Daddy, titled "Giga Daddy." The video showcases a cheerful sponge character with a prominent masculine jawline. In the background, the video features a sped-up and reverbed version of the track "Proolly my spookiest beat" by prodby668, playing on loop [14].

Figure 11: Some Other Meme Marketing Post on Scrub Daddy's Tiktok Account

METHODOLOGY

Case study approach used to compare meme marketing and viral marketing effectiveness. Two companies' content selected using simple random sampling due to irregular data sharing schedule. Analysis of marketing campaigns, focusing on brand awareness and engagement. Content analysis of marketing materials and social media posts. Quantitative data collected through companies social media accounts. Findings interpreted considering limitations of sampling method. Case study methodology provides detailed analysis of meme marketing and viral marketing.

FINDINGS

Meme marketing can foster a sense of closeness and relatability between the company and its customers by sharing the same humor and cultural references. Unlike viral videos, which may fade in popularity over time, successful memes have the potential for long-lasting impact and continued usage within online communities.

It is important to note that meme marketing should be approached with careful consideration, as inappropriate or offensive content can have negative consequences for a company's brand image. Viral videos have been highly effective over the past decade, but their production can be challenging, and there are no guarantees in viral marketing to achieving viral status even after investing a significant amount of money in advertising.

On the other hand, meme marketing requires minimal financial investment, as meme content can be created and shared without extensive production costs. Meme marketing allows for targeting a niche audience instead of attempting to reach all internet users worldwide, resulting in a more focused and potentially more engaged audience.

CONCLUSION

Theoretical Contributions

This research has made several theoretical contributions to the existing literature on marketing strategies, specifically focusing on meme marketing and viral marketing. By comparing these two approaches, the study has provided insights into their similarities, differences, and relative effectiveness. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of these strategies and their implications in the digital age. The research highlights the importance of spreadable, interesting, and entertaining content in both meme marketing and viral marketing, while

6th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress emphasizing the targeted and personalized nature of meme marketing compared to the broader reach of viral marketing. Additionally, the study contributes to the literature by exploring the role of humor, popular culture, and internet memes in marketing campaigns, and their impact on audience engagement and interaction.

Managerial Contributions

The findings of this research have practical implications for marketers and offer valuable managerial contributions. By comparing meme marketing and viral marketing, the study provides insights into the advantages and drawbacks of each strategy, helping marketers make informed decisions in selecting the most appropriate approach for their specific objectives and target audience. The research emphasizes the importance of personalization and engagement in meme marketing, suggesting that it can offer a more tailored and engaging way to connect with consumers and promote brand messaging. On the other hand, viral marketing, with its broader reach, can still be an effective strategy for creating brand awareness. By understanding the differences and potential outcomes of these strategies, marketers can develop more effective marketing campaigns that resonate with their target audience and drive meaningful engagement.

This study aims to provide a preliminary exploration of meme marketing, a relatively new concept, with a focus on two companies: Scrub Daddy and Dollar Shave Club. These companies have experienced increased sales and have actively utilized viral or meme marketing in their strategies.

While it cannot be claimed that there is a direct causality between the use of meme marketing and the increase in sales, it is important to note that while the study reveals correlations between the implementation of meme marketing and viral marketing and positive outcomes such as brand awareness and engagement, it is crucial for marketers to consider various other factors and not solely rely on these strategies for achieving increased sales.

Future Research

Firstly, conducting extensive comparative studies across industries and contexts will provide a broader understanding of the effectiveness of these strategies.

Longitudinal studies can offer insights into the long-term impact and sustainability of meme marketing and viral marketing. Industry-specific research can shed light on the effectiveness of these strategies in different sectors.

Furthermore, exploring the effectiveness of meme marketing and viral marketing on emerging platforms and understanding consumer perceptions and responses through qualitative research methods are important avenues for further investigation.

Developing standardized measurement and evaluation metrics, conducting cross-cultural and cross-national studies, and incorporating artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques can enhance the understanding and optimization of these marketing strategies.

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